

Important aspects of checkpoint inhibitors' pharmacokinetics

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Introduction

Immune checkpoint inhibitors dramatically improved the therapy of one of the deadliest diseases of today-cancer [1]. Checkpoint inhibitors release the inhibitory mechanisms that control T-cell-mediated immunity by various mechanisms, including cytotoxic T lymphocyte-associated antigen (CTLA-4) (controls T-cell activation during early stages in the lymph nodes), programmed cell death 1 (PD-1) (expressed on activated T-cells, B-lymphocytes and natural killer cells) or its ligand (PD-L1) blockade. Immune checkpoint inhibition provides patients with more durable immune responses against the tumor, which is especially important regarding tumor immune resistance in peripheral tissues [2]. Although immune-blocking anti-cancer therapies are life-saving for some patients, unfortunately, high-cost and severe adverse effects, especially immune-related ones, limit the benefits of this therapy. Data show that anti-CTLA-4-associated immune-related adverse effects are dose-related and may include one of the following: diarrhea with or without colitis (the most common), skin rash, hepatitis, endocrinopathies, uveitis, pancreatitis, nephritis, myasthenia gravis, autoimmune autonomic ganglionopathy, Guillain-Barré syndrome, sarcoidosis-like reactions, autoimmune thrombocytopenia, toxic epidermal necrolysis, and Stevens-Johnson-like syndromes. Anti-PD-1-associated immune-related side effects are less frequent, but 10% of patients develop grade 3 severity of such side effects, which in the case of hepatic, renal, ocular, neurologic, cardiovascular, rheumatologic and hematologic involvement leads to the discontinuation of the therapy [3, 4]. Here, the author summarizes available scientific data on specific aspects of checkpoint inhibitors' pharmacokinetics that could lead to improvements in immune anti-cancer therapies.

Important pharmacokinetic aspects

Anti-CTLA-4 and PD-1 blockade has been associated with more significant variations in the pharmacokinetics and efficacy in the context of individual patients' immune systems, specificity of the tumor microenvironment and metastases [5]. Although therapeutic drug monitoring has not yet been applied to immune-oncology drugs, such a strategy may be of great value, especially considering the tremendous inter-patient variability of immunotherapy-immunity-cancer interactions. Immuno-oncology drugs have a narrow therapeutic window and extensive inter-individual pharmacokinetic variability. PD-1 and PD-L1 inhibitors, such as pembrolizumab, nivolumab, cemiplimab, atezolizumab, avelumab and durvalumab, have been shown to exhibit a plateaued exposure-response curve as well as time-dependent changes in drug exposure. It has been shown that patients who respond well to immune-blocking therapy have a more significant decrease in drug clearance over time than non-responders, therefore, have supratherapeutic serum concentrations at the target tumor site [6]. Results of a study exploring the inter-individual variability in immune checkpoint inhibitors' pharmacokinetics at the population level facilitated by population pharmacokinetic modeling showed that the most commonly identified covariates on clearance were baseline body weight (BW), baseline serum albumin and sex. In contrast, BW and sex were identified as important covariates on the central volume

of distribution [7].

Results of this study showed that not only the BW has significant implications on the pharmacokinetic profile of the drug (larger the BW larger the clearance and central volume of distribution), but the albumin profile (clearance is reversely proportionate to albumin level) and biological sex (clearance and central volume of distribution are lower in females) also have significant implications. Therefore, these covariates may be included in future in silico pharmacokinetic modeling for more precise individual dose calculation. Aside from precise pharmacokinetic modeling, the cost burden of expensive biologics can be lowered by various other means, such as patent reform legislation, reference pricing, outcome-based pricing and promotion of low(er)-cost drugs prescription whenever possible [8]. It seems that reference pricing is the most effective method in reducing drug pricing, whether it is performed internally (on a national level) or externally (internationally, used by most EU countries) [9]. Other expenditure control measures are biosimilar interchangeability and substitution, open tendering and price or profit ceiling, international licensing pricing frameworks to increase national bargaining power, and value-based pricing [10].

Conclusion

Taking into account critical pharmacokinetic aspects of immune checkpoint inhibitors, and that being the significant decrease in drug clearance in patients who responded well to immune anti-cancer therapy, and as proposed by Peer and coworkers, the use of therapeutic drug monitoring, in silico pharmacokinetic modeling and estimation of drug clearance, would allow to calculate individual dose for each patient (dose of the drug could be significantly lower in responders than in non-responders) rather than using the conventional BW-dosing schemes. Such precision medicine tools could offer alternative dosing strategies with potentially less frequent and/or less severe side effects (it has been shown that anti-CTLA-4 associated immune side effects are dose-dependent) and lower cost burden (both because of the prevention of severe adverse effects and using a lower dose of the drug) while maintaining the same efficacy of the drug as with the conventional dosing regimen.

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Competing interests

The author declare no conflicts of interest.

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Abbreviations

CTLA-4, cytotoxic T lymphocyte-associated antigen; PD-1, programmed cell death 1; PD-L1, programmed cell death-ligand 1; BW, body weight.

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